

Invigilation Schedule

Of

North Western University
Faculty of Science & Technology.
Fall-2025

HSC Intake

Responsibilities of Invigilator:

1. Invigilators must be present before 30 minutes of commencing exam.
2. Invigilators who are assigned for specific room can't leave that room before the exam is finished.
3. Invigilators should be concerned during signing exam papers.
4. Invigilators must put down note in the remark box if any examinee remains absent.

NB: No students are allowed in the exam hall without admit card or permissions.

Date: 05/12/2025 Friday Time: 3:00 PM-5:15 PM Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
CSE-4215		
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 42 (Sec-A)	701	Tajul Islam, M. Raihan, Jannatul Ferdous
CSE 42 (Sec-B)	703	Nurzahan Akter Joly, Mahamudul Hassan Milon.
CSE 42 (Sec-C + R)	702	Amjad Hossain, Md. Shamim Reza
Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan		

Date: 06/12/2025 Saturday Time: 10:00 AM-12:15 PM Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
Hum-1141	EEE-1101*	CE-1113
ME-1223	Math-2231	CE-2103
CSE-2103	EEE-3101	CE-3105
Math-2231	EEE-4103*	CE-3205*
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 11 (Sec-A)	301	Md. Mausm Howlader, Sagar Kundu, Md. Abul Alal Walid

CSE 11 (Sec-B)	502	Nazirul Islam Shawon, Apurbo Saikat Roy
CSE 11 (Sec-C + R)	305	Sajib Chatterjee, Abdullah Ahmed
CSE 12 (Sec-A)	801	Dr. Kamrul Hasan Talukder, Amjad Hossain, Md. Monowar Islam.
CSE 12 (Sec-B + R)	601	Sourav Kumar kha, Md. Mahmudul Hasan, Sumaiya Jannati.
CSE 21 (Sec-A)	701	Al-Amin, Sayed Al Jubair, Md. Asaduzzaman.
CSE 21 (Sec-B)	702	Md. Sakhawat Hossain, Sharmina Al-Azad.
CSE 21 (Sec-C +R)	703	Md. Al Amin Mia Anik, Swapnil Pranta Mistry.
CSE 22 (Sec-A)	503	Nurzahan Akter Joly, Jannatul Ferdous.
CSE 22 (Sec-B + R)	501	Abu Naim Khan, Istyaque Ahammed, Md. Raihan Khan.
EEE 11 + EEE 22	602	Tajul Islam, M. Raihan.
EEE 31 + EEE 41	603	Mohammad Abdul Awal, Md. Rezanul Islam.
CE 11 + CE 21	804	Mahamudul Hassan Milon, Md. Shamim Reza.
CE 31 + CE 32	802	Md. Mahadi Hashan, Nusrat Jahan Urme.
Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan + Ashraf Hossain Sanvi + M. Asadujjaman Biplob		

Date: 06/12/2025 Saturday		
Time: 02:00 PM-04:15 PM		
Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
CSE-3101	ME-1223*	CE-1203
CSE-3211	EEE-3215*	CE-2203
CSE-4101	EEE-4255	CE-4103
		CE-4269
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 31 (Sec A)	301	Md. Mausm Howlader, Amjad Hossain, Md. Monowar Islam

CSE 31 (Sec B)	601	Md. Ahsanul Haque, Nagib Mahfuz, M. Raihan
CSE 31 (Sec-C + R)	305	Nazirul Islam Shawon, Sayed Al Jubair
CSE 32 (Sec A)	503	Dr. Md. Shahidul Islam, Tajul Islam
CSE 32 (Sec B)	502	Hafsa Siddique Nurzahan Akter Joly
CSE 32 (Sec C +R)	501	Sourav Kumar kha Sagar Kundu Apurbo Saikat Roy
CSE 41	801	Al-Amin, Abdullah Ahmed, Md. Asaduzzaman
EEE 12	602	Kamrun Nahar Arpa, Istyaque Ahammed
EEE 32 + EEE 42	603	Md. Sakhawat Hossain, Mohammad Abdul Awal
CE 12 + CE 42	804	Md. Rahatul Islam, Md. Mahadi Hashan
CE 22 + CE 41	802	Mahamudul Hassan Milon, Md. Abul Ala Walid
Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan + Ashraf Hossain Sanvi + M. Asadujjaman Biplob		

Date: 11/12/2025 Thursday		
Time: 10:00 AM-12:15 PM		
Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
Math-1131	Hum-1143	Hum-1143
CSE-1203	EEE-2205*	CE-2111
CSE-2101	EEE-3113	CE-3101*
CSE-2203	EEE-3213	CE-3209*
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 11 (Sec-A)	301	Zahid Ur Rashid Abu Naim Khan Nagib Mahfuz
CSE 11 (Sec-B)	502	Sarah Binte Hamid Tajul Islam
CSE 11 (Sec-C + R)	305	Rukaiya Bashri Md. Asaduzzaman

CSE 12 (Sec-A)	801	Dr. Rameshwar Debnath Mohammad Abdul Awal Md. Shahariar Kabir
CSE 12 (Sec-B + R)	601	Dr. Al-Mahmud Sagar Kundu M. Raihan
CSE 21 (Sec-A)	701	Mst. Shefali Khatun Amjad Hossain
CSE 21 (Sec-B)	702	Md. Shahidul Islam Swapnil Pranta Mistry
CSE 21 (Sec-C +R)	703	Md. Rezanul Islam Md. Monowar Islam
CSE 22 (Sec-A)	503	Md. Fahad Mollik Apurbo Saikat Roy
CSE 22 (Sec-B + R)	501	Md. Sohid Jaman Sumon Mahamudul Hassan Milon
EEE 11 + EEE 22	602	Md. Shamim Reza Nusrat Jahan Urme
EEE 31 + EEE 32	603	Md. Raihan Khan Md. Mahmudul Hasan
CE 11 + CE 21	804	Kazi Afra Nawer Sumaiya Jannati
CE 31 + CE 32	802	Sayed Al Jubair Abdullah Ahmed
Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan + Ashraf Hossain Sanvi + M. Asadujjaman Biplob		

Date: 11/12/2025 Thursday		
Time: 2:00 PM-04:15 PM		
Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
CSE-3105	EEE-1201	Phy-1233
Hum-3241	EEE-2103	CE-2211
CSE-4119	EEE-4235*	CE-4117*
CSE-4205		CE-4217
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 31 (Sec A)	301	Dr. Anupam Kumar Bairagi Md. Shahariar Kabir Nagib Mahfuz
CSE 31 (Sec B)	601	Md. Hasnat Hossain Mohammad Abdul Awal

CSE 31 (Sec-C + R)	305	Rukaiya Bashri Md. Mahadi Hashan
CSE 32 (Sec A)	503	Dr. Rameshwar Debnath Tajul Islam
CSE 32 (Sec B)	502	Kamrun Nahar Arpa Md. Mahmudul Hasan
CSE 32 (Sec C +R)	501	Dr. Al Mahmud Sharmina Al-Azad Swapnil Pranta Mistry
CSE 41	801	Hafsa Siddique Sagar Kundu M. Raihan
CSE 42 (Sec A)	701	Mst. Shefali Khatun Istyaque Ahammed
CSE 42 (Sec B)	703	Md. Rezanul Islam Md. Shamim Reza
CSE 42 (Sec C + R)	702	Md. Fahad Mollik, Apurbo Saikat Roy
EEE 12 + EEE 21	602	Md. Sohid Jaman Sumon Nusrat Jahan Urme
EEE 42	603	Kazi Afra Nawer Nurzahan Akter Joly
CE 12 + CE 42	804	Jannatul Ferdous Md. Shahidul Islam
CE 22 + CE 41	802	Sumaiya Jannati Abdullah Ahmed
Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan + Ashraf Hossain Sanvi + M. Asadujjaman Biplob		

Date: 15/12/2025 Monday		
Time: 10:00 AM-12:15 PM		
Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
Chem-1135 Math-1231 EEE-2121 EEE-2221	Hum-1141 EEE-2203* EEE-3121 EEE-3209	Hum-1141 Math-2131 CE-3201
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 11 (Sec-A)	301	Al-Amin Md. Shahariar Kabir M. Raihan
CSE 11 (Sec-B)	502	Sarah Binte Hamid Nusrat Jahan Urme
CSE 11 (Sec-C + R)	305	Abdullah Al Mamun

		Md. Shahidul Islam
CSE 12 (Sec-A)	801	Md. Masum Howlader Md. Raihan Khan Md. Shamim Reza
CSE 12 (Sec-B + R)	601	Rukaiya Bashri Tajul Islam Abdullah Ahmed
CSE 21 (Sec-A)	701	Md. Al Amin Mia Anik Md. Asaduzzaman
CSE 21 (Sec-B)	702	Shefali Khatun Mahamudul Hassan Milon
CSE 21 (Sec-C +R)	703	Abu Naim Khan Sayed Al Jubair
CSE 22 (Sec-A)	503	Sharmina Al-Azad Md. Rezanul Islam
CSE 22 (Sec-B + R)	501	Istyaque Ahammed Ferdouse Yesmin Pinky Sagar Kundu
EEE 11 + EEE 22	602	Sumaiya Jannati Md. Sohid Jaman Sumon
EEE 31 + EEE 32	603	Md. Mahmudul Hasan Swapnil Pranta Mistry
CE 11 + CE 21	804	Apurbo Saikat Roy Md. Fahad Mollik
CE 32	802	Jannatul Ferdous Mohammad Abdul Awal
Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan + Ashraf Hossain Sanvi + M. Asadujjaman Biplob		

Date: 15/12/2025 Monday		
Time: 2:00 PM-04:15 PM		
Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
Hum-3141	Phy-1233	Chem-1235
CSE-3203	EEE-2105	CE-2209
CSE-4103	Hum-4143	CE-4109*
CSE-4201	EEE-4225	CE-4261*
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator

CSE 31 (Sec A)	301	Al-Amin Nusrat Jahan Urme Md. Rezanul Islam
CSE 31 (Sec B)	601	Md. Hasnat Hossain Nagib Mahfuz Sagar Kundu
CSE 31 (Sec-C + R)	305	Sarah Binte Hamid Md. Shahariar Kabir
CSE 32 (Sec A)	503	Md. Masum Howlader Sayed Al Jubair
CSE 32 (Sec B)	502	Rukaiya Bashri Md. Raihan Khan
CSE 32 (Sec C +R)	501	Kamrun Nahar Arpa Md. Asaduzzaman Mahamudul Hassan Milon
CSE 41	801	Abu Naim Khan Jannatul Ferdous Tajul Islam
CSE 42 (Sec A)	701	Sharmina Al-Azad Ferdouse Yesmin Pinky
CSE 42 (Sec B)	703	Istyaque Ahammed Nurzahan Akter Joly
CSE 42 (Sec C + R)	702	Sumaiya Jannati Abdullah Ahmed
EEE 12 + EEE 21	602	Md. Mahmudul Hasan Md. Mahadi Hashan
EEE 41 + EEE 42	603	Swapnil Pranta Mistry Mohammad Abdul Awal
CE 12 + CE 42	804	Md. Sohid Jaman Sumon Md. Shahidul Islam
CE 22 + CE 41	802	Apurbo Saikat Roy Md. Fahad Mollik

Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan + Ashraf Hossain Sanvi + M. Asadujjaman Biplob

Date: 18/12/2025 Thursday Time: 10:00 AM-12:15 PM Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
Phy-1133		
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 11 (Sec A)	301	M. Raihan Kazi Afra Nawer Md. Shahariar Kabir
CSE 11 (Sec B)	502	Mahamudul Hassan Milon Md. Shamim Reza
CSE 11 (Sec C + R)	305	Md. Asaduzzaman Md. Sohid Jaman Sumon
Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan		

Date: 19/12/2025 Friday Time: 10:00 AM-12:15 PM Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
Phy-1233 Math-2131 Hum-2241	Math-1131 EEE-2101* Hum-2241 Hum-3141 EEE-3201* EEE-4115 EEE-4241	Math-1131 Hum-2147* CE-3103 CE-3207
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 12 (Sec-A)	901	Md. Sohid Jaman Sumon Apurbo Saikat Roy
CSE 12 (Sec-B + R)	601	Abu Naim Khan Md. Fahad Mollik
CSE 21 (Sec-A)	701	Sajib Chatterjee Abdullah Ahmed
CSE 21 (Sec-B)	702	Sayed Al Jubair Dr. Ismail Saifullah
CSE 21 (Sec-C +R)	703	Nafis Ahmed Pantho Nusrat Jahan Urme
CSE 22 (Sec-A)	503	Abdullah Al Mamun Sharmina Al-Azad
CSE 22 (Sec-B + R)	501	Md. Mahadi Hashan Jannatul Ferdous

EEE 11 + EEE 21 + EEE 22	602	Ferdouse Yesmin Pinky Kazi Afra Nawer
EEE 31 + EEE 32 + EEE 41	603	Swapnil Pranta Mistry Md. Mahmudul Hasan
EEE 42	903	Md. Shahidul Islam Md. Raihan Khan
CE 11 + CE 21	904	Md. Monowar Islam Sumaiya Jannati
CE 31 + CE 32	902	Amjad Hossain Istyaque Ahammed
Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan + Ashraf Hossain Sanvi + M. Asadujjaman Biplob		

Date: 19/12/2025 Friday		
Time: 03:00 PM-05:15 PM		
Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
CSE-3103		Hum-2247 Hum-4247
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 31 (Sec-A)	301	Md. Hasnat Hossain Sayed Al Jubair Md. Mahadi Hashan
CSE 31 (Sec-B)	601	Sajib Chatterjee Md. Shahidul Islam Ferdouse Yesmin Pinky
CSE 31 (Sec-C + R)	305	Kamrun Nahar Arpa Amjad Hossain
CE 22 + CE 42	702	Nafis Ahmed Pantho Md. Monowar Islam
Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan + Asadujjaman Biplob		

Date: 22/12/2025 Monday		
Time: 10:00 AM-12:15 PM		
Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
CSE-4117		
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 41	801	Sagar Kundu Faisal Habibi Raim Mishon Chandra Das

Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan		

Date: 23/12/2025 Tuesday		
Time: 10:00 AM-12:15 PM		
Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
Hum-1143 EEE-1221 CSE-2105 CSE-2201 CSE-3109	Chem-1135 EEE-2211 EEE-3103 EEE-3207 EEE-4201	Phy-1133 CSE-2123 CE-3109
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 11 (Sec-A)	301	Mishon Chandra Das Md. Shahariar Kabir
CSE 11 (Sec-B)	502	Faisal Habibi Raim Tajul Islam
CSE 11 (Sec-C + R)	305	Abdullah Al Mamun M. Raihan
CSE 12 (Sec-A)	801	Tasnia Tabassum Lamisa Nurzahan Akter Joly
CSE 12 (Sec-B + R)	601	Mamun Abdullah Abdullah Ahmed
CSE 21 (Sec-A)	701	Sourav Kumar Kha Nagib Mahfuz
CSE 21 (Sec-B)	702	Md. Ahsanul Haque Jannatul Ferdous
CSE 21 (Sec-C +R)	703	Md. Shamim Reza Abu Naim Khan
CSE 22 (Sec-A)	503	Ferdouse Yesmin Pinky Apurbo Saikat Roy
CSE 22 (Sec-B + R)	501	Md. Rezanul Islam Sharmina Al-Azad Mohammad Abdul Awal
CSE 31 (Sec A)	901	Md. Sohid Jaman Sumon Sagar Kundu
CSE 31 (Sec B)	902	Md. Fahad Mollik Nusrat Jahan Urme
CSE 31 (Sec C1)	903	Md. Raihan Khan

		Istyaque Ahammed
CSE 31 (Sec C2)	904	Kazi Afra Nawer Sumaiya Jannati
EEE 11 + EEE 22	602	Md. Asaduzzaman Mahamudul Hassan Milon
EEE 31 + EEE 32 + EEE 42	603	Md. Shahidul Islam Swapnil Pranta Mistry
CE 11 + CE 21	804	Md. Monowar Islam Md. Mahmudul Hasan
CE 32	802	Amjad Hossain Md. Mahadi Hashan
Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan + Ashraf Hossain Sanvi + M. Asadujjaman Biplob		

Date: 23/12/2025 Tuesday		
Time: 02:00 PM-04:15 PM		
Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
Hum-3243 Hum-4241	Math-1231 Math-2131 EEE-4107	Math-1231 Math-2231 Hum-4147
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 32 (Sec A)	503	Mishon Chandra Das Md. Mahadi Hashan
CSE 32 (Sec B)	502	Faisal Habibi Raim Md. Sohid Jaman Sumon
CSE 32 (Sec C + R)	501	Dr. Anupam Kumar Bairagi Md. Shahariar Kabir Ferdouse Yesmin Pinky
CSE 42 (Sec A)	701	Mamun Abdullah Md. Rezanul Islam
CSE 42 (Sec B)	703	Sourav Kumar Kha Md. Fahad Mollik
CSE 42 (Sec C + R)	702	Md. Ahsanul Haque Md. Raihan Khan
EEE 12 + EEE 21	602	Amjad Hossain Sagar Kundu
EEE 41	603	Md. Monowar Islam Kazi Afra Nawer

CE 12 + CE 22	804	Md. Shamim Reza Md. Asaduzzaman
CE 41	802	Md. Shahidul Islam Mahamudul Hassan Milon
Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan + Ashraf Hossain Sanvi + M. Asadujjaman Biplob		

Date: 26/12/2025 Friday		
Time: 10:00 AM-12:15 PM		
Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
CSE-1201		
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 12 (Sec-A)	801	Faisla Habibi Raim Abdullah Al Mamun Md. Shamim Reza
CSE 12 (Sec-B + R)	601	Tasnia Tabassum Lamisa Dr. Ismail Saifullah Md. Shahariar Kabir
Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan		

Date: 26/12/2025 Friday		
Time: 03:00 AM-05:15 PM		
Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
CSE-3121		
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 31 (Sec-A)	301	Faisla Habibi Raim Ferdouse Yesmin Pinky Md. Shamim Reza
CSE 31 (Sec-B)	601	Dr. Shahidul Islam Apurbo Saikat Roy Md. Fahad Mollik
CSE 31 (Sec-C + R)	305	Imran Rahman Ifty Md. Sohid Jaman Sumon
Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan		

Date: 27/12/2025 Saturday Time: 10:00 AM-12:15 PM Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
CSE-1101 CSE-2107 CSE-2205	Phy-1133 Hum-2141 Hum-3241	Hum-1145 CE-2115 CE-3111 CE-3203
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 11 (Sec A)	301	Mishon Chandra Das Md. Shahariar Kabir Mahamudul Hassan Milon
CSE 11 (Sec B)	502	Tasnia Tabassum Lamisa Md. Asaduzzaman
CSE 11 (Sec C + R)	305	Faisal habibi Raim Sumaiya Jannati
CSE 21 (Sec A)	701	Nafis Ahmed Pantho Sagar Kundu
CSE 21 (Sec B)	702	Md. Rahatul Islam Apurbo Saikat Roy
CSE 21 (Sec C + R)	703	Sharmina Al-Azad Istyaque Ahammed
CSE 22 (Sec A)	503	Nurzahan Akter Joly Nusrat Jahan Urme
CSE 22 (Sec B + R)	501	Abdullah Al Mamun Ferdouse Yesmin Pinky Nagib Mahfuz
EEE 11 + EEE 21	602	Abu Naim Khan Kazi Afra Nawer
EEE 32	603	Tajul Islam Md. Mahmudul Hasan
CE 11 + CE 21	804	Jannatul Ferdous Md. Monowar Islam
CE 31 + CE 32	802	Md. Raihan Khan Md. Mahadi Hashan
Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan + Ashraf Hossain Sanvi + M. Asadujjaman Biplob		

Date: 27/12/2025 Saturday		
Time: 02:00 PM-04:15 PM		
Program: Bachelor of Science (HSC Intake)		
Dept. of CSE	Dept. of EEE	Dept. of CE
CSE-3201 CSE-4105	CSE-1221 EEE-2215 EEE-4101	EEE-1221 CE-4107 CE-4279
Dept. & Semester	Room no.	Name of invigilator
CSE 32 (Sec A)	503	Mishon Chandra Das Sagar Kundu
CSE 32 (Sec B)	502	Md. Ahsanul Haque Md. Raihan Khan
CSE 32 (Sec C +R)	501	Nafis Ahmed Pantho Sharmina Al-Azad Md. Mahmudul Hasan
CSE 41	801	Md. Rahatul Islam Ferdouse Yesmin Pinky Md. Shahidul Islam
EEE 12 + EEE 22	602	Jannatul Ferdous Md. Fahad Mollik
EEE 41	603	Nurzahan Akter Joly Kazi Afra Nawer
CE 12 + CE 42	804	Abu Naim Khan Sayed Al Jubair
CE 41	802	Tajul Islam Md. Shahariar Kabir
Reserved Invigilator : Md. Mahedi Hasan + Ashraf Hossain Sanvi + M. Asadujjaman Biplob		

Nagib Mahfuz
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